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Research Article

**FORMULATION AND EVALUATION OF FLOATING
TABLETS OF PENTOXIFYLLINE**N. Shirisha Reddy^{1*}, Dr. J. Ramesh¹¹Department Of Pharmaceutics, Omega College Of Pharmacy, Edulabad, Hyderabad (Telangana)**Article Received: August 2024 Accepted: September 2024 Published: October 2024****Abstract:**

The objective of this research is to formulate and develop gastro retentive floating tablets of Pentoxifylline using polymers by effervescent system which will retain the drug up to 12hrs to prepare and evaluate floating tablets of Pentoxifylline using polymers like HPMC, Ethyl Cellulose and Xantham Gum and sodium bicarbonate is used as effervescent component tablets were compressed by direct compression method. The prepared tablets showed acceptable physic chemical characteristics floating characteristics (floating lag time, floating time) drug content and evaluated for in vitro release characteristics for 12hours in 0.1N HCL. Drug compatibility with excipients was checked by FTIR studies. Formulation with prepared with HPMC polymer was retarding the drug release up to 12hrs P3 release 99.83%. From the release kinetics data it was evident that the formulation followed Higuchi release mechanism.

Keywords: Pentoxifylline, HPMC, Ethyl Cellulose and Xantham Gum**Corresponding author:****N. Shirisha Reddy,**

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INTRODUCTION:

Oral drug delivery system is aid to arrive to resistance to change of position therapeutic plasma drug concentration in to the preparation. These drug dosage forms disclose good patient compliance and assumption drug release profiles. Moreover these were not constructed to counter the difficulties attached with physiological position of the human body that are gastric emptying which more important effectual the bioavailability and in turn the curative capacity to produce a desired effectual of the drug dosage forms. Thus gastro retentive dosage forms such as hydrodynamic balanced systems, modify density system, GIT release the drug in absorption zone and extended the gastric residence duration by antagonistic gastric emptying method. The groups can controller release of the drug in absorption zone before eviction of the dosage form from the human body thence make proper the bioavailability of the drug.

Gastric emptying of dosage forms is an utmost various method and capability to extended and control emptying time is vital plus for dosage forms, which domicile in the stomach for a large time than conventional dosage forms, while the dosage form is lower absorption/non absorbing phase. These kinds of problems defeat by the floating drug delivery system. It is the gastro retentive drug delivery system.

Gastro-retentive system:

Gastro retentive system can stay in the gastric site for many hours and thence importantly extended the gastric retention made better bioavailability minimize drug wastage and make better, solubility of drugs that

are lesssoluble in high pH environment. Gastric retention generate newer curative possibilities and substantial profits from patients.

Gastro-retentive system are those dosage form which is able for retain itself in the stomach of gastric content to maximizing the produce absorption drug from medium of acidic in control manner.

Gastro retentive system are favourable drug which is improving their:

- Bioavailability
- Therapeutic effective
- Possible reduction
- Reduces drug wastage
- Rise solubility for drug that are less soluble in high pH

Floating drug delivery system:

Floating drug delivery system are less density which buoyancy is capable amount for float over the gastric content. It stay buoyant in stomach without affective gastric empty retention time. Conclusion maximize the gastric retention time for better control of fluctuation in plasma drug concentration.

Devis is primarily introduce the floating system that floating drug delivery system to use the difficulty of swelling of dosage form and presented the modern gastro retentive drug delivery system to the pharmaceutical or pharmacy industry. Today the more of effectual control drug release dosage form.

Floating drug delivery system:

The main purpose of floating drug delivery system is arrive assuming and maximize in bioavailability. Today pharmaceutical scientist are mostly participate in development of floating drug delivery system. The dosage form has vantage of once dose for cure and should be deliver the active drug material directly at specific site. Floating system is beneficial as drug with narrow absorption window, which is importance for local action to other dosage form of tablets which are absorbed in the stomach. Floating drug delivery system will maximize the bioavailability of the drug from by floating dosage form in the stomach for large duration and produce for extended time and these several kinds of system are significant for narrow absorption. Useful the special category of the dosage form. Gastric emptying is most fast in fasting stage, bulky in the presence of food to slow emptying and give important liquid for efficient buoyancy.

Needs of floating drug delivery system:

- The Transitional gastric emptying time is reason of drug absorption.
- Drugs which are absorbed from the site of gastro intestinal tract.
- Local delivery system or sustained drug delivery system from the stomach.
- Drugs which are low soluble or degrade in alkaline. They are encounter at the gastro intestinal lower part.
- Mostly applied in cure in peptic ulcer.

Ideal characteristics of floating drug delivery system:

- The floating drug delivery system is should be maximize the bioavailability.
- It should be provide beneficial systematic effectual.
- Applied of those substance which provide maximum bioavailability.
- Drugs, which are primarily absorbed in the stomach and upper site of gastro intestine.
- The absorption of drug in gastro intestine tract with narrow window absorption.
- The drug acts local in the stomach.
- The drug which are unstable in the colon.
- Should be enhancement effectual for in treatment and should be low adverse effect.
- It should be nice stability.

Importance of floating drug delivery system:

- Drug dosing is low
- The adverse effect of drug is low
- The cure of gastric disorder is useful.

- The dosage form of drug is applicable for firstly absorbed in gastro retentive intestinal tract.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

Pentoxifylline Praveen Laboratories Pvt Ltd, Gujarat., Provided from SURA LABS, Dilsukhnagar, HPMC Corel Pharma,Ahmedabad, India. S , Ethyl Cellulose-Strides Arcolab, Bangalore ,Xantham Gum Vishal Pharma, Vadodara, India , Sodium Bi carbonate-M/S Seeko Biotech, Vijayawada, India , Citric acid-Merck Specialities Pvt Ltd, Mumbai, India, Talc -Merck Specialities Pvt Ltd, Mumbai, India ,Mg Stearate-Trishul reagents and chemicals, Chennai, Lactose-S.S chemicals, Chennai

METHODOLOGY:**Analytical method development:****a) Determination of absorption maxima:**

A solution containing the concentration 10 µg/ mL drug was prepared in 0.1N HCL UV spectrum was taken using Double beam UV/VIS spectrophotometer. The solution was scanned in the range of 200 – 400 nm.

b) Preparation calibration curve:

10mg Pentoxifylline pure drug was dissolved in 10ml of methanol (stock solution1) from stock solution 1ml of solution was taken and made up with10ml of 0.1N HCL (100µg/ml). From this 1ml was taken and made up with 10 ml of 0.1N HCL (10µg/ml). The above solution was subsequently diluted with 0.1N HCL to obtain series of dilutions Containing 10, 20, 30, 40, 50µg /ml of per ml of solution. The absorbance of the above dilutions was measured at 273 nm by using UV-Spectrophotometer taking 0.1N HCL as blank. Then a graph was plotted by taking Concentration on X-Axis and Absorbance on Y-Axis which gives a straight-line Linearity of standard curve was assessed from the square of correlation coefficient (R²) which determined by least-square linear regression analysis.

Pre-formulation parameters

The quality of tablet, once formulated by rule, is generally dictated by the quality of physicochemical properties of blends. There are many formulations and process variables involved in mixing and all these can affect the characteristics of blends produced. The various characteristics of blends tested as per Pharmacopoeia.

Angle of repose:

The frictional force in a loose powder can be measured by the angle of repose. It is defined as, the maximum angle possible between the surface of the pile of the powder and the horizontal plane. If more powder is added to the pile, it slides down the sides of the pile

until the mutual friction of the particles producing a surface angle, is in equilibrium with the gravitational force. The fixed funnel method was employed to measure the angle of repose. A funnel was secured with its tip at a given height (h), above a graph paper that is placed on a flat horizontal surface. The blend was carefully pored through the funnel until the apex of the

conical pile just touches the tip of the funnel. The radius (r) of the base of the conical pile was measured. The angle of repose was calculated using the following formula:

$$\tan \theta = h / r \quad \tan \theta = \text{Angle of repose}$$

h = Height of the cone, r
= Radius of the cone base

Table : Angle of Repose values (as per USP)

Angle of Repose	Nature of Flow
<25	Excellent
25-30	Good
30-40	Passable
>40	Very poor

Bulk density:

Density is defined as weight per unit volume. Bulk density, is defined as the mass of the powder divided by the bulk volume and is expressed as gm/cm³. The bulk density of a powder primarily depends on particle size distribution, particle shape and the tendency of particles to adhere together. Bulk density is very important in the size of containers needed for handling, shipping, and storage of raw material and blend. It is also important in size blending equipment. 10 gm powder blend was sieved and introduced into a dry 20 ml cylinder, without compacting. The powder was carefully leveled without compacting and the unsettled apparent volume, V_o, was read.

The bulk density was calculated using the formula:

$$\text{Bulk Density} = M / V_o$$

Where, M = weight of sample, V_o = apparent volume of powder

Tapped density:

After carrying out the procedure as given in the measurement of bulk density the cylinder containing the sample was tapped using a suitable mechanical tapped density tester that provides 100 drops per minute and this was repeated until difference between

succeeding measurement is less than 2 % and then tapped volume, V measured, to the nearest graduated unit. The tapped density was calculated, in gm per L, using the formula:

$$\text{Tap} = M / V$$

Where, Tap= Tapped Density

M = Weight of sample, V= Tapped volume of powder

Measures of powder compressibility:

The Compressibility Index (Carr's Index) is a measure of the propensity of a powder to be compressed. It is determined from the bulk and tapped densities. In theory, the less compressible a material the more flowable it is. As such, it is measures of the relative importance of inter particulate interactions. In a free-flowing powder, such interactions are generally less significant, and the bulk and tapped densities will be closer in value.

These differences are reflected in the Compressibility Index which is calculated using the following formulas:

$$\text{Carr's Index} = [(\text{tap} - b) / \text{tap}] \times 100$$

Where, b = Bulk Density, Tap = Tapped Density

Table: Carr's index value (as per USP)

Carr's index	Properties
5 – 15	Excellent
12 – 16	Good
18 – 21	Fair to Passable
2 – 35	Poor
33 – 38	Very Poor
>40	Very Very Poor

Formulation development of floating Tablets:

Procedure for direct compression method:

- 1) Drug and all other ingredients were individually passed through sieve no □ 60.
- 2) All the ingredients were mixed thoroughly by triturating up to 15 min.
- 3) The powder mixture was lubricated with talc.
- 4) The tablets were prepared by using direct compression method by using 8mm punch

Formulation of tablets:**Table: Formulation composition for Floating tablets**

Ingredients	P1	P2	P3	P4	P5	P6	P7	P8	P9
Pentoxifylline	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100
HPMC	25	50	75	-	-	-	-	-	-
Ethyl Cellulose	-	-	-	25	50	75	-	-	-
Xantham Gum	-	-	-	-	-	-	25	50	75
Sodium Bi carbonate	20	20	20	20	20	20	20	20	20
Citric acid	15	15	15	15	15	15	15	15	15
Talc	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10
Mg Stearate	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5
Lactose	225	200	175	225	200	175	225	200	175
Total Weight	400	400	400	400	400	400	400	400	400

All the quantities were in mg

RESULT AND DISCUSSION:**Analytical Method**

a. Determination of absorption maxima : The standard curve is based on the spectrophotometry. The maximum absorption was observed at 273 nm.

b. calibration curve: Graphs of Pentoxifylline was taken in 0.1N HCL (pH 1.2)

Table: Observations for graph of Pentoxifylline in 0.1N HCL

Conc[$\mu\text{g/mL}$]	Abs
0	0
10	0.133
20	0.265
30	0.389
40	0.518
50	0.649

Fig : Standard graph of Pentoxifylline in 0.1N HCL

Standard graph of Pentoxifylline was plotted as per the procedure in experimental method and its linearity is shown in Table and Fig. The standard graph of Pentoxifylline showed good linearity with R^2 of 0.999, which indicates that it obeys "Beer- Lambert's" law.

Preformulation parameters of powder blend:

Table: Pre-formulation parameters of blend

Formulation Code	Angle of Repose	Bulk density (gm/mL)	Tapped density (gm/mL)	Carr's index (%)	Hausner's Ratio
P1	24.62±0.90	0.325±0.00	0.399±0.00	17.20±0.12	1.21±0.02
P2	28.58±0.94	0.334±0.01	0.428±0.003	22.16±1.20	1.30±0.09
P3	27.78±0.780	0.362±0.01	0.4712±0.01	20.82±0.07	1.28±0.07
P4	28.97±0.86	0.3330±0.01	0.410±0.01	20.24±1.49	1.26±0.019
P5	28.47±0.92	0.334±0.01	0.4527±0.00	19.88±0.331	1.24±0.04
P6	26.89±0.92	0.319±0.024	0.377±0.00	16.62±0.32	1.201±0.019
P7	21.62±0.53	0.342±0.012	0.380±0.00	21.89±0.56	1.23±0.021
P8	19.08±0.72	0.345±0.01	0.442±0.01	18.24±0.16	1.22±0.001
P9	27.89±0.80	0.348±0.01	0.416±0.01	16.27±0.039	1.19±0.022

Tablet powder blend was subjected to various pre-formulation parameters. The angle of repose values indicates that the powder blend has good flow properties. The bulk density of all the formulations was found to be in the range of 0.319±0.024 to 0.348±0.01 (gm/ml) showing that the powder has good flow properties. The tapped density of all the formulations was found to be in the range of 0.410±0.01 to 0.4527±0.00 showing the powder has good flow properties. The compressibility index of all the formulations was found to be below 19 which

shows that the powder has good flow properties. All the formulations has shown the hausners ratio ranging between 1.12 to 1.22 indicating the powder has good flow properties.

Quality Control Parameters For tablets:

Tablet quality control tests such as weight variation, hardness, and friability, thickness, Drug content and drug release studies were performed for floating tablets.

In vitro quality control parameters

Formulation codes	Average Weight (mg)	Hardness(kg/cm ²)	Friability (%loss)	Thickness (mm)	Drug content (%)	Floating lag time (min)	Total Floating Time(Hrs)
P1	398.32	4.28	0.36	2.78	98.52	4.36	12
P2	399.22	4.33	0.42	2.63	99.34	4.22	12
P3	400.13	4.22	0.31	2.51	99.47	3.85	12
P4	401.28	4.38	0.52	2.72	97.39	3.93	12
P5	398.65	4.29	0.44	2.58	98.68	4.57	12
P6	399.45	4.51	0.38	2.64	97.22	4.92	12
P7	405.68	4.38	0.37	2.77	98.63	3.99	12
P8	395.37	4.26	0.48	2.63	99.38	4.28	12
P9	397.29	4.51	0.53	2.83	97.23	4.39	12

All the parameters for SR layer such as weight variation, friability, hardness, thickness, drug content were found to be within limits.

Figure: Floating lag time (min)

Figure: Total Floating Time (Hrs)

In Vitro Drug Release Studies**Table: Dissolution data of Floating Tablet**

Time(Hrs)	P1	P2	P3	P4	P5	P6	P7	P8	P9
0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
0.5	10.11	14.76	18.93	9.07	11.34	18.87	12.34	15.84	19.09
1	13.32	19.66	22.61	15.29	19.68	24.14	18.56	21.93	24.61
2	18.22	24.35	28.37	21.65	25.66	31.62	22.68	26.85	32.36
3	22.89	29.92	34.22	26.92	34.27	37.25	29.39	33.26	44.21
4	28.36	33.72	38.53	31.44	39.18	42.15	34.23	39.15	52.78
5	34.47	39.53	44.67	37.17	48.32	51.34	38.32	43.68	58.46
6	42.05	48.86	51.25	42.38	54.62	59.42	42.75	49.12	65.85
7	51.92	56.77	62.41	48.51	61.38	67.38	47.22	54.78	73.67
8	59.88	63.62	71.88	55.66	65.27	71.39	52.40	59.42	79.31
9	64.73	74.92	85.93	68.83	72.48	77.78	57.75	64.26	85.22
10	72.36	81.18	92.64	76.92	79.68	83.54	62.16	71.18	89.08
11	83.19	89.43	94.71	88.24	90.34	88.73	69.50	77.53	92.13
12	90.25	95.28	99.83	97.36	93.28	91.75	72.43	86.44	95.15

Fig: Dissolution data of Pentoxifylline Floating tablets containing HPMC

Fig: Dissolution data of Pentoxifylline Floating tablets containing Ethyl Cellulose

Fig: Dissolution data of Pentoxifylline Floating tablets containing Xantham Gum

Whereas the formulations prepared P1 - P3 with HPMC K-100M retarded the drug release up to 12 hours in the concentration 75 mg. concentrations the

polymer was to retard the drug release is P3 is 99.83%.

Whereas the formulations prepared P4 - P6 with Ethyl

cellulose retarded the drug release up to 12 hours in the concentration 25 mg. concentrations the polymer was to retard the drug release is P4 is 97.36% .

Whereas the formulations prepared P7 - P9 with Xanthan Gum retarded the drug release up to 12 hours in the concentration 75 mg. concentrations the

polymer was to retard the drug release is P9 is 95.15% .

Hence from the above dissolution data it was concluded that P3 formulation was considered as optimised formulation because good drug release (99.83%) in 12 hours.

Application of Release Rate Kinetics to Dissolution Data for optimised formulation:

Table : Application kinetics for optimised formulation

CUMULATIVE(%) RELEASE Q	TIME (T)	ROOT (T)	LOG(%) RELEASE	LOG (T)	LOG (%) REMAIN	RELEASE RATE (CUMULATIVE % RELEASE / t)	1/CUM% RELEASE	PEPPAS log Q/100	% Drug Remaining	Q01/3	Qt1/3	Q01/3- Qt1/3
0	0	0			2.000				100	4.642	4.642	0.000
18.93	0.5	0.707	1.277	-0.301	1.909	37.860	0.0528	-0.723	81.07	4.642	4.328	0.314
22.61	1	1.000	1.354	0.000	1.889	22.610	0.0442	-0.646	77.39	4.642	4.261	0.380
28.37	2	1.414	1.453	0.301	1.855	14.185	0.0352	-0.547	71.63	4.642	4.153	0.489
34.22	3	1.732	1.534	0.477	1.818	11.407	0.0292	-0.466	65.78	4.642	4.037	0.605
38.53	4	2.000	1.586	0.602	1.789	9.633	0.0260	-0.414	61.47	4.642	3.947	0.695
44.67	5	2.236	1.650	0.699	1.743	8.934	0.0224	-0.350	55.33	4.642	3.811	0.831
51.25	6	2.449	1.710	0.778	1.688	8.542	0.0195	-0.290	48.75	4.642	3.653	0.989
62.41	7	2.646	1.795	0.845	1.575	8.916	0.0160	-0.205	37.59	4.642	3.350	1.292
71.88	8	2.828	1.857	0.903	1.449	8.985	0.0139	-0.143	28.12	4.642	3.041	1.601
85.93	9	3.000	1.934	0.954	1.148	9.548	0.0116	-0.066	14.07	4.642	2.414	2.227
92.64	10	3.162	1.967	1.000	0.867	9.264	0.0108	-0.033	7.36	4.642	1.945	2.696
94.71	11	3.317	1.976	1.041	0.723	8.610	0.0106	-0.024	5.29	4.642	1.742	2.899
99.83	12	3.464	1.999	1.079	-0.770	8.319	0.0100	-0.001	0.17	4.642	0.554	4.088

Fig : Zero order release kinetics

Fig: Higuchi release kinetics

Fig: Kors mayer peppas release kinetics

Fig: First order release kinetics

Optimised formulation P3 was kept for release kinetic studies. From the above graphs it was evident that the formulation P3 was followed Higuchi release mechanism.

Drug – Excipient compatibility studies

Fourier Transform-Infrared Spectroscopy:

Figure: FTIR Spectrum of pure drug

There was no disappearance of any characteristic peak in the FTIR spectrum of drug and the polymers used. This shows that there is no chemical interaction between the drug and the polymers used. The presence of peaks at the expected range confirms that the materials taken for the study are genuine and there were no possible interactions.

Pentoxifylline are also present in the physical mixture, which indicates that there is no interaction between

drug and the polymers, which confirms the stability of the drug.

CONCLUSION:

Pentoxifylline reduce leg pain caused by poor blood circulation. It was prepared using different polymers like HPMC, Ethyl Cellulose and Xanthan Gum and in combination, sodium bicarbonate and citric acid for floating purpose Talc, Magnesium stearate and Lactose

used as excipients and formulation was developed by direct compression method. The prepared tablet were evaluated for various physical parameters floating properties, swelling ability and drug release. Hence from the dissolution data it was concluded that P3 Formulation was considered as optimized formulation because of controlled and maximum drug release 99.83 in 12 hours. P3 formulation contains Drug Pentoxifylline 100mg and HPMC 75mg. The dissolution data was subjected to release rate kinetics and it was found that the optimized formulation P3 follows Higuchi release mechanism.

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